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Research Article

**CORRELATION OF CONVERSION DISORDERS WITH SIZE
OF FAMILY AND BIRTH ORDER**¹Dr Muhammad Jahanzaib, ²Dr Muhammad Sajid Qasim, ³Dr Muhammad Ummail Abbas
¹Mayo Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** March 2019**Accepted:** April 2019**Published:** May 2019**Abstract:**

Objectives: The aim of this research work is to determine the size of family & birth order of the patients having CD (Conversion Disorder) and to check its association with the pattern of symptoms of conversion and co-morbid symptoms of depression and anxiety.

Study Design: This was a descriptive transverse research work conducted in hospital.

Venue & duration: This research work was carried out in psychiatry department of Mayo Hospital Lahore. The duration of this research work was from September 2017 to February 2019.

Methodology: Evaluation of total 100 patients having CD identified on the basis of DSM-4 carried out for the pattern of symptoms. An interview conducted with the patients to gather the description about the size of family and birth order. HADS (hospital anxiety & depression scale) was in use for the assessment of the symptoms of anxiety & depression.

Results: Most of the patients were available with four to 6 siblings. There was a strong association between the large size of family and patients who were middle born with the pattern of symptoms of CD as well as the symptoms of depression and anxiety.

Conclusion: The people with identification of the CD require the management for not only the aspects related to psychology but also for the issue of social life as size of family and anxieties linked with these issues.

Keywords: Siblings, Psychology, Unconsciousness, Identification, Anxiety, Evaluation, Psychology.

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INTRODUCTION:

CD is a health issue which appears with the motor, sensory, pseudo-seizure or blended signs caused by stress in the non-availability of some physical complication [1]. About 80.0% patients reported a trauma in their lives [2], which might have happened in the previous times as physical abuse in their childhood [3], or currently before the start of the disease [4]. Mainly the causing features for this disease contained, sexual or physical abuse during childhood days, any trauma in adult days, stress of academic exams or failure in examination, fight with spouse, conflicts inside the person and hardships of daily routine life [5, 6]. Normally CD appeared with seizure like signs or unconsciousness fits [4, 7-9] as there was report of their rate from 40.30% to 41.30% [10, 11] followed by 40.30% rate for sensory signs, 12.60% for blended signs [11] and only 5.0% patients suffering from CD appeared with the motor symptoms.

It is better known that the rate of infant & maternal mortality rises with the enhancement in the number of deliveries and low interval between the deliveries [12, 13]. Better development in the physical and mental health, health condition and psychological wellbeing of person based upon the family and support from these social circle [14] which require appropriate size of family and proper structure [12, 15, 16]. In the similar manner negative association was available between mood and the amount of the children [14]. The children which are born in middle of working mothers have advantages over 1st and last born child as well as the children of non-employed mothers [17]. The occurrence of the main psychiatric disease was very high among the persons who belonged to the 3rd birth order [18].

Among adolescents of Kuwait, there is a positive association of the size of family and birth order with

the anxiety [19]. There is very low amount of studies available about this subject. The social support is very much important for the mental wellbeing of the persons. This research work aimed to determine the relationship of size of family & birth order with the CD.

METHODOLOGY:

This was an elaborate, transverse hospital based research work. This research work carried out in psychiatry department, Mayo Hospital, Lahore. The duration of this research work was from September 2017 to February 2019. There were total one hundred patients from both genders as identified by 2 psychiatrists as the victim of CD on the basis of the diagnostic standard of the DSMIV. We arranged an interview with the patients for the assessment of the demographical information and appearance of the symptoms of conversion like motor, sensory, pseudo-seizure & blended symptoms. HADS Urdu version was in use for the assessment of the symptoms of anxiety and depression [20-22].

This standard was in use to record the subjective evaluation of the symptoms of depression and anxiety. The reading of the questions carried out for the patients who were illiterate. Rates, frequencies, averages, SD, ANOVA, T test were in use for the representation of the information. SPSS V. 10 was in use for the analysis of the collected information.

RESULTS:

The findings display that 28.0% patients suffering from CD were available with one to three siblings, 50.0% patients were available with four to six siblings and 22.0% patients were available with four to six siblings as elaborated in Table-1.

Table-I: Percentage of the Sample Regarding Number of Siblings

No. of siblings	Percent	Chi Square
1 to 3	28.0	-
4 to 6	50.0	-
7 and above	22.0	13.04 *

* denotes p-value <0.001

Regarding the pattern of CD, pseudo-seizures were available in 12.0% (n: 22) patients having one to three siblings, 53.0% (n: 22) were available with four to six siblings and 8.0% (n: 19) patients have seven or more children. Chi square method displayed that there was no important association amount of the children & pseudo-seizures. Sensory symptoms were very frequent available in 56.0% (n: 18) patients available with four to six siblings. Chi square method displayed that there was an important association between amount of children & sensory symptoms.

Mild motor signs were available in the patients having one to three children while moderate & severe nature were very frequent with four to six children. Chi square displayed an important association between the amount of children & motor symptoms. Blended symptoms were available more in patients having four to six children 60.0% (n: 29). Chi square displayed that there was important association between amount of children & blended symptoms as available in Table-2.

Table-II: Association of Pattern of Conversion Disorder with the Number of Siblings

No. of siblings	Pseudo seizure		Sensory Symptoms		Motor Symptoms		Mixed Symptoms	
	%	Chi Sq.	%	Chi Sq.	%	Chi Sq.	%	Chi Sq.
1 to 3	29.00	0.83	19.00	0.001	10.00	0.01	25.00	0.1
4 to 6	52.00	-	69.00	-	71.00	-	60.00	-
7 & above	19.00	-	12.00	-	19.00	-	14.00	-

Symptoms of anxiety & depression were very frequent among the patients having four to six children as 58.0% (n: 38) & 45.0% (n: 28) correspondingly. Chi

square displayed no important association between the amount of children and symptoms of depression as available in Table-3.

Table-III: Association of Anxiety and Depressive Symptoms with the No of siblings in Conversion Disorder

No of Siblings	Anxiety		Depression	
	freq	Chi Sq.	freq	Chi Sq.
1 to 3	14.0	0.060	18.0	0.570
4 to 6	38.0	-	28.0	-
7 and above	14.0	-	15.0	-

Results displayed that twenty-four percent patients with CD were first born, 56.0% patients were born in middle & 20.0% patients were born in last. This displayed that CD was very frequent in the patients which were middle born. Chi-square method displayed there was an important association between CD &

birth order. The findings showed that there was no important association between the symptoms of anxiety and patients of birth order but an important association was available between the symptoms of depression & birth order as presented in Table-4.

Table-IV: Association Of Anxiety and Depressive Symptoms with the Birth Order of the Sample

Birth order	Anxiety					Depression					
	Present		Absent			Present		Absent			Chi Sq.
	freq	percent	freq	percent	Chi Sq.	freq	percent	freq	percent		
First	12.0	18.00	8.0	24.00	0.431	16.0	26.00	4.0	10.00	0.032	
Middle	40.0	60.00	16.0	47.00		35.0	57.00	21.0	54.00		
Last	14.0	21.00	10.0	29.00		10.0	16.00	14.0	36.00		

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this research work displayed that about half amount of the study population was belonging to the size of family from four to six children. They were more likely to face the symptoms of sensory & motor of CD. In addition, greater than 50.0% patients were belonging to the middle order according to the concern of the birth order & these patients were available with more anxiety in comparison with the patients with depression. Adler concluded that certain styles of life commonly develop as a purpose of ordinal position of the patient in the whole family. Adler also emphasized on the same positions of the child but his major area of concern was the development of the personality and not any particular psychiatric complication.

There are many particular personalities among the patients suffering from CD which should be a matter of research work in further cases [23]. In current research work, patients with four to six children were more likely to appear with various types of symptoms of CD in comparison with those patients having shorter or big size of family. The disparity was because of the fact that 50.0% specimens of the current research work contained patients with four to six children and only 1/5th samples were belonging to the families of big size. There is no comparison of the other studies with the results of this work as the birth order in CD was not the point of attention in those research works and they emphasized the physical condition of the specimen of the study. Amazingly the patients with four to six children were importantly more likely to available with symptoms sensory & motor in comparison with the pseudo-seizures & blended symptoms [12]. The patients with this complication and from various cultures appeared with various symptom pattern [15].

The findings of this research work displayed the middle as the very vulnerable which is same with the result of a study conducted in Kuwaiti [19]. Ahmed in his research work depending upon the main psychiatric abnormalities, which are not comparable with the current research work [18].

CONCLUSIONS:

The findings of this research work conclude that for a suitable administration & better long-term findings of CD, satisfactory thoughtful of the family physiology as well structure of the patients is the requirement. The screening of these patients is necessary and their treatment for the co-morbid symptoms of depression & anxiety is also necessary.

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